

Molluscicidal and Bactericidal Agents : VI—Synthesis of Some New Phenoxy Heterocyclic Compounds

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Manuscript received 25 September 1978, revised 29 December 1978, accepted 12 February 1979

A series of substituted phenoxyacid chlorides were condensed with 2-aminothiazoles and 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles giving N-(2-thiazolyl)phenoxyacetamides(I) and N-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)phenoxyacetamides(II) respectively. Cycloaddition of the acid chlorides on 2-arylideneaminothiazoles(III) and 2-arylideneamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles(IV) yielded a new series of substituted 3-phenoxy-4-phenyl-1-(2-thiazolyl)azetidinones(V) and 3-phenoxy-4-phenyl-1-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl) azetidinones(VI). The amides (I and II) have been screened against *Bulinus truncatus* and the azetidinones (V and VI) tested against some strains of bacteria and fungi. The results of screening showed that, most of the thiazole derivatives(I) gave high LC 50 and LC 90 molluscicidal activity. The antibacterial results of the azetidinones (V) and (VI) showed a variable activity against a gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria.

SCHISTOSOMIASIS or Bilharziasis, is a widespread parasitic human disease. It infects about 200 million people all over the world, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions¹.

In Egypt, it is estimated that about 65% of the population are infected, and is the cause, directly or indirectly of 25% of all the deaths in the country².

The molluscicidal activity of different heterocyclic compounds including imidazolyl³, pyridyl⁴, iminodithiolyl⁵, 8-quinolyl⁶, benzoxazines⁷, thiazolyl⁸ and isothiazolyl⁹ derivatives have been reported in the patent literature. Recently, acetamides were reported to possess molluscicidal activities¹⁰. It was therefore of interest to attempt the preparation of some new N-(2-thiazolyl)phenoxyacetamides and N-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)phenoxyacetamides for screening against schistosomiasis.

Experimental

The infrared (ir) absorption spectra were determined in KBr with a Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer. Melting points are uncorrected.

Preparation of Phenoxyacetyl Chlorides.

These compounds were prepared according to literature methods^{1,2-14}.

Preparation of 2-aminothiazoles and 2-aminothiadiazoles :

These compounds were prepared according to the literature methods^{15,16}.

The Reaction of Phenoxyacetyl Chlorides with 2-aminothiazoles and 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles :

[The acid chloride (0.001 mole) was dissolved in dry benzene (10 ml) and the resulting solution added with stirring to a mixture of the 2-aminothiazoles (or the 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles) (0.001 mole) and triethylamine (0.001 mole) in dry benzene (20 ml). Stirring was continued for 5 hrs at 40-50° and then left overnight. The triethylammonium chloride was filtered off, washed with benzene and the filtrate and washings concentrated under reduced pressure. The precipitated amide was collected, washed with 10% sodium carbonate and crystallised from alcohol (Tables 1 and 2).

Synthesis of 2-arylideneaminothiazoles(III) and 2-arylideneamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles(IV) :

A mixture of the amine (0.1 mole) and the aromatic aldehyde (0.1 mole) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) containing two drops of piperidine was refluxed for 5 hrs. The precipitate was collected, washed and crystallised from ethanol (Tables 3 and 4).

The Reaction of 2-arylideneaminothiazoles and 2-arylideneamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles with Phenoxyacetyl Chlorides.

Synthesis of Substituted 3-phenoxy-4-phenyl-1-(2-thiazolyl)azetidinones(V) and 3-phenoxy-4-phenyl-1-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)azetidinones(VI).

To a mixture of the Schiff bases(III) or (IV) (0.02 mole) and triethylamine (0.01 mole) in dry benzene (30 ml), a solution of the phenoxyacetyl chloride (0.01 mole) in dry benzene (20 ml) was

TABLE 1—N-(2-THIAZOLYL)PHENOXYACETAMIDES(I)

Compound No. (I)	R	R ¹	R ²	m.p. °C	Yield %	Solvent of Crystallisation
a	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	H	165-6	40	A
b	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	H	160-1	30	A
c	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	H	169-70	35	A
d	H	C ₆ H ₅	H	155-6	45	B
e	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	H	196-8	32	B
f	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	H	140-1	25	A
g	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃	H	169-70	53	A/B
h	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃	H	82-3	33	P
i	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	H	175-6	15	A
j	H	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	H	112-8	65	P
k	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	H	142-3	10	B
l	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	H	139-40	17	P
m	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	115-6	59	A
n	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	145-6	57	B
o	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	162-3	57	B
p	H	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	119-20	30	A
q	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	152-3	32	A
r	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	135-6	57	A
s	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	CH ₃	80-1	61	A
t	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	CH ₃	145-6	44	B
u	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	CH ₃	174-5	16	A/B
v	H	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	CH ₃	137-8	38	A/B
w	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	CH ₃	182-3	27	P
x	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	CH ₃	139-40	35	A

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

A = alcohol, B = Benzole, P = Petroleum ether (80/100) and A/B = Alcohol/Benzole (2 : 1).

added during $\frac{1}{2}$ hr and the mixture stirred for 3 hrs. Triethylammonium chloride was filtered off, washed several times with benzene and the filtrate and washings evaporated under reduced pressure. The semisolid residue was treated with petroleum ether/ether (1 : 1) (3 × 30 ml) to remove any unreacted Schiff base, the resulting solid was digested with boiling ethanol (100 ml) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr and the product filtered off (Tables 5 and 6).

TABLE 2

N-(1,3,4-THIADIAZOL-2-YL)PHENOXYACETAMIDES(II)					
Compound No. (II)	R	R ²	m.p. °C	Yield %	Solvent of Crystallisation
a	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	210-11	10	A
b	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	199-200	12	A
c	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	183-5	20	A
d	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	218-20	14	A

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. A = Alcohol.

TABLE 3—2-ARYLIDENEAMINOTHIAZOLES(III)

Compound No. (III)	R ¹	R ²	R ³	m.p. °C	Yield %	Solvent of Crystallization
a	C ₆ H ₅	H	<i>o</i> -OH-C ₆ H ₄	113-4	70	A
b	C ₆ H ₅	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	88-9	75	A
c	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₆ H ₄ CH=CH-	142-3	75	A
d	C ₆ H ₅	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	138-9	72	A
e	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	H	<i>o</i> -OH-C ₆ H ₄	171-2	79	A
f	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	118-9	68	A
g	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	H	C ₆ H ₄ CH=CH	130-1	85	A
h	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	138-9	80	A
i	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	121-2	82	A
j	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OH-C ₆ H ₄	103-4	90	A
k	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ CH=CH	108-9	88	A
l	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	155-6	88	A

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. A = Alcohol.

TABLE 4—2-ARYLIDENEAMINO-1,3,4-THIAZOLINES(IV)

Compound No. (IV)	R ^a	R ^b	m.p. °C	Yield %	Solvent of Crystallisation
a	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	146-8	40	A/B
b	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	191-2	50	A/B
c	C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	172-4	45	A/B
d	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	170-2	25	A/B

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.
A/B=Alcohol/Benzole (2 : 1).

directly. Condensation with the 2-aminothiazoles and 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles in dry benzene in presence of triethylamine gave the corresponding N-(2-thiazolyl)phenoxyacetamides(I) and N-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl) phenoxyacetamides(II).

R = H, *o*-Cl, *p*-Cl, *o*-NO₂, *p*-NO₂ and *p*-CH₃

Discussion

The phenoxyacetic acid chlorides were prepared from the phenoxyacetic acids, and thionyl chloride in dry benzene and employed for the synthesis

The structure of the compounds (I and II) was confirmed by elemental analysis and ir spectra which showed a well defined absorption band near

TABLE 5—3-PHENOXY-4-PHENYL-1-(2-THIAZOLYL)AZETIDINONES(V)

Compound No. (V)	R	R ^a	R ^b	R ^c	m.p. °C	Yield %	Solvent of Crystallization
a	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	H	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	123-4	9	D
b	H	C ₆ H ₅	H	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	120-2	12	D
c	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	H	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	133-4	10	B
d	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	70-2	13	B
e	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	145-7	18	B
f	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	129-30	33	D
g	H	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	149-50	32	D
h	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	68-70	38	B
i	H	C ₆ H ₅	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	177-9	30	B
j	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	145-7	22	B
k	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	92-3	53	B
l	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	173-4	10	B
m	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	170-1	12	D
n	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	70-2	73	D
o	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	160-2	7	D
p	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	136-8	6	B
q	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₆ H ₅ -CH=CH-	168-9	36	D
r	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	<i>p</i> -OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	202-4	8	B
s	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	188-90	21	A/B
t	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	60-2	16	B
u	H	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	69-70	31	D
v	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	105-6	6	D
w	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	170-8	13	A/B
x	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	123-5	11	D
y	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	140-1	12	D
z	H	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	80-90	50	D

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.
D=dioxane, B=Benzole, A/B=alcohol/Benzole (2 : 1).

TABLE 6—3-PHENOXY-4-PHENYL-1-(1,3,4-THIAZOL-2-YL)AZETIDINONES(VI)

Compound No. (VI)	R	R ^a	R ^b	m.p. °C	Yield %	Solvent of Crystallisation
a	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	138-40	6	D
b	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	120-2	22	D
c	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	118-9	11	B
d	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	150-2	10	D
e	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	228-30	6	D
i	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	173-5	14	B
g	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	241-2		B
h	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	228-30	6	B
i	<i>p</i> -Cl	OH ₂	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	138-40	5	D
j	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	150-1	12	D

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.
D=dioxane ; B=Benzole.

1720-1690 cm^{-1} (C=O), 1550 cm^{-1} (COHN), a sharp band near 3480-3380 cm^{-1} (NH) and a band at about 1280 cm^{-1} (ArO)¹¹.

The discovery of the β -lactam antibiotics initiated research into the preparation and chemical and biological properties of 2-azetidiones. Hence 2-arylideneaminothiazoles(III) and 2-arylideneamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles(IV), were prepared and condensed,

with the phenoxyacid chlorides in dry dioxane in presence of triethylamine giving 3-phenoxy-4-phenyl-1-(2-thiazolyl)azetidiones(V) and 3-phenoxy-4-phenyl-1-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)azetidiones(VI).

Identification of the azetidiones(V) and (VI) was confirmed by elemental analysis and ir spectroscopy which showed absorption bands at about 1775-1740 cm^{-1} monocyclic β -lactam (C=O) and at 1280-1278 cm^{-1} (ArO)¹¹.

Biological Results :

Substituted N-(2-thiazolyl)phenoxyacetamides(I) and N-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)phenoxyacetamides(II) were tested against *Bulinus trauncatus*.^{*} Most of the thiazole derivatives showed high LC 50 and LC 90 molluscicidal activity, except these compounds containing strong electron releasing groups on the benzene ring. All the N-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)phenoxyacetamides(II) showed no activity on snails below a concentration of 250 ppm after 5 days exposure.

The molluscicidal activity of N-(2-thiazolyl)phenoxyacetamides(I) plotted against Hammett

values, for the phenyl substituents showed a linear relationship.

The antibacterial screening of the azetidiones(V) and (VI) showed variable activity against *Bacillus cereus*, *Sarcina*, *Bacillus megaterium* and *Bacillus subtilis*.

The antifungal activity of the azetidiones(V) and (VI) against *Aspergillus niger*, *Mucor circinelloides*, *Curvularia lanata*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Fusarium semitectum* show the following :

(i) All the 1-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)azetidiones(VI) were inactive, (ii) Most of the 1-(2-thiazolyl)azetidiones(V) showed remarkable activity.

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* The screening of these compounds was carried out at 18° for 24 hrs exposure followed by washing with water.